

GES4SEAS POLICY BRIEF #7

OCEAN OPTIMISM – HOW WE ALL CAN BUILD ON OUR KNOWLEDGE FOR A BETTER FUTURE FOR OCEANS

How can this Policy Brief support you?

Despite many studies showing the way in which the oceans are degraded and have been subjected to many pressures emanating from human activities, it is beholden on all stakeholders to demonstrate how the oceans can be restored to a state which both protects and maintains their natural features as well as sustainably delivering the goods and benefits required by society. Furthermore, there is the need for increased ocean literacy to allow all stakeholders and society at large a role in ocean protection. Natural scientists have many tools and approaches to determine the problems in the marine environment whereas solutions to those problems will come from social sciences, governance and engineering. This Policy Brief shows marine environmental managers and all other stakeholders that despite the many threats to the seas, there is cause for optimism with tangible improvements and current and proposed national, European and international initiatives. These allow us all to change our narrative about the ocean status, from a pessimistic view to a positive action.

Key Messages

The ocean is facing multiple pressures from human activities, including the effects of climate change.

Science has a pre-eminent role in identifying problems and communicating these to society.

However, scientists are also increasingly taking an active role in developing solutions, including strategies for adapting to and mitigating climate change, protecting the ocean, restoring degraded habitats, increasing food security and reducing pollution.

Co-creating these solutions with society changes our narrative about the ocean, motivates actions from managers and provides hope for marine ecosystems.

Narrative of the problem, with GES4SEAS examples

Building on the knowledge generated in GES4SEAS, we can move toward a more integrated and forward-looking approach to ocean stewardship that connects ecosystem functioning, services and human well-being. Evidence linking biodiversity, climate and food systems highlights the need for solutions that simultaneously address multiple pressures, while ecosystem-based management (EBM) tools and decision-support systems enable tailored, context-specific actions. Understanding tipping points, cumulative pressures and recovery processes (e.g., benthic restoration or eutrophication mitigation) allows us to anticipate change and design adaptive, resilient management strategies.

To strengthen this foundation, future efforts should focus on evaluating management effectiveness, applying clear success criteria and aligning actions with frameworks such as the EU Nature Restoration Regulation goals. Co-designed solutions, including spatial planning, fisheries management and citizen science, can improve both ecological outcomes and societal acceptance. Empowering scientists as communicators and advocates also helps to bridge the persistent gap between science, policy and society.

Equally crucial is transforming how we frame ocean challenges. Rather than emphasizing only decline, we should adopt a balanced narrative, such as #OceanOptimism, that acknowledges risks while showcasing recovery, innovation and achievable solutions. Highlighting success stories, ecosystem resilience and tangible benefits fosters hope, engagement and collective responsibility.

By shifting from a crisis-only narrative to one of informed action and opportunity, we can better motivate decision-makers and citizens to contribute to a sustainable ocean future, where protection and use are not in conflict, but part of a shared vision of thriving marine systems for nature and humans.

Figure 1. The path from adaptive management to #OceanOptimism by co-creation with all stakeholders at all stages

Policy implications

European Directives

- Marine Strategy Framework Directive
- Maritime Spatial Planning Directive
- Natura 200 Directives
- Strategic Environmental Assessment Directive
- Nature Restoration Regulation
- Common Fisheries Policy

Other Policy / International Objectives

- Regional Seas Conventions (and QSR)
- International Council for the Exploration of the Seas (ecological status)
- World Ocean Assessment III
- UNEP Sustainable Blue Economy IOC/UNESCO State of the Ocean Report 2024
- Sustainable Development Goals (All)

Beyond the State of Art

Over the past four years, GES4SEAS has advanced beyond the state-of-the-art by moving from fragmented, pressure-based assessments toward an integrated understanding of marine ecosystems as providers of interconnected services and human benefits. It has strengthened the scientific basis for linking ecosystem functioning, biodiversity and socio-economic outcomes, enabling a more holistic view of ocean sustainability. The project has also operationalised EBM through practical tools and decision-support systems (e.g. SEAS4GES), allowing policies to be tailored, transparent and measurable (e.g. using Tikta software in assessing the status). The solutions will come from the GES4SEAS analysis of the continuum from an Ecosystem-Based Approach (EBA) to EBM and using Ecosystem-Based Technical Measures (EBTM) and Programmes of Measures (PoM) with good and fit-for-purpose Ecosystem-Based Sciences (EBS) and communication to all stakeholders through Ocean Literacy.

Importantly, GES4SEAS has contributed to anticipating ecological change, through the analysis of tipping points, cumulative pressures and recovery trajectories, shifting management from reactive to proactive. It has demonstrated that effectiveness can and must be evaluated (e.g. using Tikta), providing clearer criteria for success in marine management and restoration efforts. The integration of emerging approaches, such as remote sensing, modelling and citizen science, has further expanded monitoring capacity and societal participation.

Beyond scientific and technical progress, a key innovation has been in communication. Building on concepts such as #OceanOptimism and science–policy bridging, GES4SEAS has helped to reframe the ocean narrative from one dominated by decline to one that balances challenges with science-based solutions, resilience and recovery. It has empowered scientists as communicators and ocean advocates, while fostering ocean literacy and stakeholder engagement.

Traditional methods of communicating complex scientific issues regarding the challenges facing our marine environments often fail to resonate with society, creating a gap between expert knowledge and public engagement. To address this, the GES4SEAS project has used Ocean Literacy tools, such as online Massive Online Open Courses (MOOCs) and comic books for young audiences, to simplify complex topics such as EBM and cumulative pressures, and to foster ‘Emoceans’ (the emotional connection between individuals and the sea). Empirical evidence from three European case studies, within the GES4SEAS project, indicate that visual narratives can enhance engagement and support understanding of complex marine topics. These outcomes demonstrate the value of initiatives transferring from a narrative of ‘doom and gloom’ to one of “Ocean Optimism” to motivate the next generation of marine stewards.

This shift in narrative is transformative: it promotes positive views over despair, it highlights that management works when applied effectively and it showcases tangible pathways to restoration and sustainable use of the ocean. By aligning robust science, actionable tools and positive communication, GES4SEAS has laid the foundation for a future in which society not only understands ocean problems but is motivated and equipped to solve them.

Figure 2. The role of each player in developing, advising, communicating and achieving successful and sustainable marine management (from Borja et al. 2025 Front. Commun.)

Recommendations and example actions and solutions for ocean problems, which can be implemented by stakeholders.

<p>Social actions & solutions</p>	<p>Raise awareness of society/stakeholders & change behaviour, through Ocean Literacy and examples of success in protecting, conserving and restoring the ocean across the world</p> <p>Increase participation & engagement of society/stakeholders in taking decisions from the beginning of the participatory processes</p> <p>Fight the ‘fake news’ & misunderstanding with good evidence & good science, working with science journalists and environmental influencers</p> <p>As solutions can affect beliefs, emotions, etc., scientists must adopt a transdisciplinary basis, including social, economic & environmental scientists</p> <p>Change the narrative when transmitting messages to society, identifying the problems, identifying the positive examples & providing solutions attractive to media with examples of success</p> <p>Solutions must be equitable, inclusive & ethical</p> <p>It is necessary to link human & ocean health approach to solutions (see GES4SEAS Policy Brief #5)</p>
--	---

Environmental actions & solutions	<p>Combine global & local solutions, in protection, restoration, conservation & climate change, but solutions must be context specific</p> <p>Maintain long-term monitoring networks to take knowledge-based management decisions when deciding measures, & promote open-access of data & publications</p> <p>Restore hydrology, habitats & species; increase connectivity (not only among marine protected areas, but in general), especially those contributing more to CO₂ sequestration</p> <p>Avoid ‘gardening’ solutions, & include solutions considering functionality of the systems as well as the recovery of ecosystem services & resilience</p> <p>Increase the protection of the ocean (at least 30% of its area), not only coastal areas but also deep-seas & open-seas</p>
Economic actions & solutions	<p>Blue economy & activities at sea must consider assimilative & carrying capacity, & marine spatial planning must ensure sustainability i.e. maintaining good environmental status of the sea</p> <p>Eliminate overexploitation, with better management of fishing (including multispecies & ecosystem-based management)</p> <p>Apply prevention (circular economy), mitigation (collection, monitoring, etc.) & adaptation</p> <p>Create motivation & incentives for new & good practices & disincentive bad ones</p>
Technology & policy actions & solutions	<p>Adopt technological solutions to reduce emissions, to remove litter, to restore ecosystems & to handle large amounts of data (e.g., artificial intelligence, machine learning, & big data)</p> <p>Increase effective international cooperation (take advantage of Green Deal, Sustainable Development Goals, Decade of Ocean Science, Decade on Ecosystems Restoration, etc.)</p> <p>Implement appropriate policies: Water Clean Act, Oceans Act, Water Framework Directive, Marine Strategy Framework Directive, Maritime Spatial Planning Directive, Biodiversity Strategy, Nature Restoration Regulation, Regional Seas Conventions, international legislation, etc.</p>

Key Facts

Effective science communication bridges the gap between marine research and policymaking and hence requires clear, objective, fit-for-purpose and engaged communication of scientific findings to policymakers and society to counter misinformation and promote informed decision-making processes.

Multiple communication channels are needed to reach diverse audiences with clear, jargon-free language and engaging methods, tending to a holistic approach combining logical evidence-based with the emotional engagement of society.

Ocean literacy is key in raising public awareness and promoting behavioural changes for a new narrative on the future of the ocean.

Increased funding is required for science communication, engaging early with target audiences, ensuring high quality scientific evidence and presenting positive and negative aspects of findings, and objectively showing the emotional side of the stories.

Public support for marine protection and conservation, as well as restoration policies can be enhanced, leading to effective management of marine ecosystems.

Authors:

Borja, A., Knowlton, N., Micheli, F., Uyarra, M.C., Smith, G., Berg, T., Leal, M.C., Elliott, M.
doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20510406

References from GES4SEAS

For GES4SEAS resources and references click this [link](#) or scan this QR code.

For references from outside GES4SEAS see:

Borja, A. et al. (2022). *Front. Mar. Sci.*, 9:886027.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.886027>

For additional resources from the GES4SEAS project, visit the web page: <https://www.ges4seas.eu>

For more information about these and other GES4SEAS publications, scan the QR code

